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**BUYING BEHAVIOR OF CONSUMER TOWARDS HANDLOOM AND HANDCRAFT
WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO CIDCO URBAN
HAAT PROJECT NAVI MUMBAI**

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Abstract:

This research presents results of a survey focusing on study of the target consumers' buying behavior towards handlooms and handicrafts of CIDCO's (City and Industrial Development Corporation of Maharashtra) Urban Haat project which is the part of Government of India's policy to set up permanent marketing infrastructure at prime locations in the country to eliminate middle agencies. Understanding Consumer Buying Behavior offers greater satisfaction to consumers. We assume that the project has adopted the Marketing Concept, purchase decision process and is consumer oriented. The purpose of this survey was to identify target consumers, factors influencing purchase decision process and to analyze is product meet target consumer's requirements. Therefore survey was conducted through close ended questionnaire from random sampling size of 100 respondents. It has been found that young female and male those are the professionals with middle class family are the target consumers who have greater influence on purchase decision process of handloom and handcraft product.. But their needs are not fully fulfilled due to price and variety factors. And high class consumers are not attracted in this process.

Key words: *Urban Haat, buying behavior, handlooms, handcraft, purchase decision process*

I. Introduction

Consumer behavior is the study of how individuals, groups and organizations select, buy, use, and dispose of goods, service, ideas, or experiences to satisfy their needs and wants.

<http://www.stefan-reindl.com>

Recently, consumers have been undergoing a major transformation from passive buyers to active enhancers or creators of new consumption experiences, proactively taking part in the

process of collaborative marketing. The experiential paradigm of consumer behavior views consumption as a holistic expression of symbolic meanings, hedonic (emotional) responses, and sensory pleasures (Hirschman & Holbrook, 1986; Holbrook & Hirschman, 1982).

A consumer's buying behavior is influenced by cultural, social, personal and psychological factors. Most of these factors are uncontrollable and beyond the hands of marketers but they have to be considered while trying to understand the complex behavior of the consumers. Consumer is the study of the processes involved when individuals or groups select, purchase, use, or dispose of products, services, ideas, or experiences to satisfy needs and desires" (Solomon 1995, 7).

The manner in which consumer buys is extremely important to marketers. It involves understanding the set of decisions (what, why, when, how much and how often) that consumer makes over the time (Hoyer 2004).

The Indian handicrafts are universally acknowledged to be the very best and also as the true symbol of the spirit of the country. At present India is one of the major players in the global handicrafts market. There are mainly five export-oriented crafts. They are: Hand knitted woolen carpet Art metal-ware Cane and Bamboo products Hand printed textile Wood-wares. This clearly indicates the tremendous export potential of the handicraft market"

("Role of Rural Sectors in Indian Economy", Dr. Pervez H. Zaidi & Anis Fatima, Kurukshetra, December, 1999.)

Ogunnaike, O. (2010) studied Nigerian Perceptions of locally made textile products of Kaduna State and mentioned local textile company. This study identified some perceptual variables affecting buying behavior and explores influence of marketing strategies on consumer perception.

I. CIDCO Project in Navi Mumbai

The City and Industrial Development Corporation of Maharashtra Ltd., was a necessity and Navi Mumbai- the land of comforts and luxuries - is its invention. In the decade of 1951-61 population of Mumbai rose by 40 per cent and in the corresponding decade it shot up by 43.80

percent. The rapid growth rate of population made possible by the increasing industrial and commercial importance of the city, resulted in a fast deterioration in the quality of life for the majority of people living in the city. Development inputs could not keep pace with the rapidly growing population, industry, trade and commerce. Besides, there were physical limitations to the growth of the city built on long and narrow peninsula, which had very few connections with the mainland.

Urban Haat

Urban Haat is an ever-permanent fair for Crafts, Food and Cultural Activities. The craftsmen from various areas and the cultural happenings provide a panoramic view of richness and diversity of handicrafts and artifacts.

The project is a part of Government of India's policy to set up permanent marketing infrastructure at prime locations in the country to eliminate middle agencies. Urban Haat project confirms the prescribed policy details. Development Commissioner Handlooms and Development Commissioner Handicrafts are the coordinators and Development Commissioner Handicrafts is the nodal agency for implementation. For Maharashtra State, Maharashtra Small Scale Industries Development Commission (MSSIDC) is the nodal agency for co-ordination.

This project is funded directly by Government of India, Ministry of Textiles to the tune of 70% of the estimated cost. Remaining 30% or the actual expenditure has to be borne by the implementing agency.

III Purchase Decision Model

In an early study of the buyer decision process literature, Frank Nicosia (Nicosia, F. 1966; pp 9–21) identified three types of buyer decision making models. They are the univariate model (He called it the "simple scheme".) in which only one behavioral determinant was allowed in a stimulus-response type of relationship; the multi-variate model (He called it a "reduced form scheme".) in which numerous independent variables were assumed to determine buyer behavior; and finally the "system of equations" model (He called it a "structural scheme" or "process scheme".) in which numerous functional relations (either univariate or multi-variate) interact in a complex system of equations. He concluded that only this third type of model is capable of expressing the complexity of buyer decision processes. In chapter 7, Nicosia builds a

comprehensive model involving five modules. The encoding module includes determinants like "attributes of the brand", "environmental factors", "consumer's attributes", "attributes of the organization", and "attributes of the message". Other modules in the system include consumer decoding, search and evaluation, decision, and consumption.

IV. Knowledge Area Gaps

Consumers are buying this product which is easily available in this Urban Haat. Yet there is reluctance to make the buying decision for the handloom and handcraft products. Purchase decision model is used to understand the buyer response and to determine buyer behaviour. According to this model if brand attributes are high, consumers' attributes and environmental factors are influence to purchase decision process, yet consumer buying reluctance exists in this project.

V. Research Questions

- i) A research is required to know how much target consumers requirements are really meet by the product.
- ii) It would help understand to know about which group of consumers dislike the product.
- iii) It would be important to know the characteristics to which these consumer factors are related
- iv) It would be important to identify the problems encountered in this process.

VI. Objectives Of The Study

- i) To find out the target consumers who prefers and believes in the handlooms and handcraft product artifacts.
- ii) To study consumer buying behavior and factors which influence the purchase decision process.
- iii) To analyze the future prospect for the consumers to get better handloom and handcraft product to meet their requirements.

VII. Key Concepts

Research Methodology

The research methodology adopted is based on primary data through which the most recent and accurate piece of information is collected through survey. The main tool used was, the structured questionnaire method with close-ended questions for conducting survey to get response from 100 consumers. Sampling design adopted is random sampling. The questionnaire was formulated by keeping in mind the respondents' co-operation and identifying needs to be known. The secondary data used from books, journals magazines, newspapers and websites etc., have been used to support primary data wherever needed.

TOOLS - Questionnaire

- Demographic Data
- Items measuring Purchase decision process
- Buying behavior

Data Analysis

Some of the questions are as follow.

- What is your age?
- What is your gender?
- What is your occupation?
- What is your monthly income?
- Do you like to buy handloom and handcraft?
- Where do you prefer to buy the same product?
- What are the features you look for in a product before making purchase decision?
- How long you have been using this product?
- When do you purchase?
- How would you rate the experience of purchase?

What is your age?

Table No. 1

Age	No. of Respondents
Below 20	8
21-30	26
31-40	41
41-50	18
51 and Above	7

What is your gender?

Table No. 2

Gender	Age of Respondents
Male	47
Female	53

What is your occupation?

Table No. 3

Occupation	No. of Respondents
Student	9
Professionals	55
Businessman	3
Other	33

What is your monthly income?

Table No. 4

Income	No. of Respondents
Below 25000	25
25000-50000	31
50000-75000	11
75000 & Above	11

Do you like to buy handloom and handcraft?

Table No. 5

Category	No. of Respondents
Yes	89
No	11

Where do you purchase to buy the same product?

Table No. 6

Category	No. of Respondents
Departmental Store	21
Urban Haat	73

6 respondents not given their response

How long you have been using this product?

Table No. 7

Category	No. of Respondents
1 Year	41
2 Year	23
3 Year	10
4 Year	14

When do you purchase?

Table No. 8

Category	No. of Respondents
Need	34
Impulse	36
During Festival	15
Occasion	16

What are the features you look for in a product before making purchase decision?

Table No. 9

Category	No. of Respondents
Pro Quality	71
Price	33
Variety	30
Any Other	0

How would you rate the experience of purchase?

Table No. 10

Category	No. of Respondents
Satisfied	76
Highly Satisfied	7
Dissatisfied	2
Highly Dissatisfied	1
Neutral	12

IV. Conclusions

It has been demonstrated through table no. 1, 2, 3, 4 and their graphs that young female and male consumers playing vital role in this CIDCO Urban Haat Project and those are professionals with middle class family who have greater influence on purchase decision process of handloom and handcraft product. This study has been proved that high class consumers are almost not involved in this process through table no. 4. Therefore it is need to focus on this issue to make success the purpose. Though all target consumers are satisfied with this product quality but they are not happy with product price and variety. These are problems encountered through this study and also there is need to well understand the target consumers' requirements.

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